

Homework as an Artifact: Understanding the Assumptions Behind Homework Practices

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Abstract

Homework has been assigned to students for over a century, but its benefits are still debated. Viewing homework as an educational artefact reveals its broader cultural significance and traditions. This study aims to examine homework in contemporary educational contexts comprehensively. It explores the history of homework and ongoing debates about its efficacy. Additionally, it investigates the assumptions and beliefs guiding teachers' homework implementation and how this impacts effectiveness. A literature review gathered insights on homework's history and perceptions. Interviews, focus groups, and observations examined teachers' attitudes and behaviours about assigning homework. Qualitative analysis identified patterns and themes related to homework. Research shows mixed evidence regarding homework's academic benefits, especially for younger students. However, some nonacademic benefits are indicated. Teachers' assumptions about homework often go unexamined despite shaping implementation. More training on intentional, differentiated homework practices is recommended. Homework norms and assumptions should be evaluated against modern educational values. Teacher training on tailoring homework purposefully is needed. Schools should align homework policies with learning goals.

Keywords: Students homework; Educational artefact; Home assignments; Writing tasks; Educational elements.

Introduction

Homework has long been a staple of education, with students lugging backpacks full of worksheets and textbooks to complete at home after school. But we rarely stop to examine homework as more than just a task to be completed. Viewing homework as an artefact allows us to consider its broader cultural and historical significance. Homework has been a common practice in schools for over a century, with students spending several hours after school completing assignments at home (Vatterott, 2009).

The purpose of homework ranges from practising skills taught in class to developing study habits and personal responsibility (Carr, 2013). However, the benefits of homework have been debated, with some arguing that it improves academic achievement while others find little to no impact on grades. Homework policies vary between teachers, schools, districts, and even countries. Despite mixed evidence, homework remains a core educational tradition.

For many students, homework epitomizes the drudgery and boredom associated with schooling. Scribbled math equations, highlighted passages, and dog-eared textbooks contain traces of late nights, frustration, and diligence. Homework artefacts tell stories about striving and struggling. For parents, homework artefacts like dioramas or short writing assignments provide glimpses into their children's development and school lives. Teachers amass piles of homework to grade, quantifying achievement and knowledge.

But homework artefacts also illuminate changing educational values and philosophies. The shift from rote memorization to critical thinking and analysis can be seen in essay assignments, while the increasing focus on standardized testing and accountability is evident in practice worksheets. Homework encompasses individuals' experiences while reflecting broader societal priorities and trends (Kohn, 2006; Ramdass & Zimmerman, 2011).

As mundane as it may seem, homework offers a window into the enterprise of education. Scrutinizing it as more than busy work reveals homework's place in culture, history, and the narratives of our educational lives.

Significance of the study

Exploring the value of homework as an essential part of school culture is a question that needs an answer. While some teachers consider homework a vital assessment and learning tool, others consider it a complementary teaching aid that will probably foster knowledge in the curricula throughout the learning journey. Following the Schein model in analyzing the three levels of culture, this paper sheds light on the justifications, beliefs, and underlying assumptions behind the degree of the assigned value of homework in a Palestinian school as an effective tool for quality learning.

Aims

This study aims to investigate homework comprehensively within contemporary educational contexts. Firstly, it seeks to study the history of homework, from its ancient origins to its current manifestation. It sheds the light on its development over time. Secondly, it explores the ongoing debates surrounding the efficacy of homework, considering diverse perspectives and empirical evidence. Additionally, it aims to uncover the underlying assumptions and beliefs that guide teachers' implementation of homework, exploring how these perceptions influence its effectiveness and impact on student achievement. Furthermore, the study aims to scrutinize the characteristics of homework as an educational artefact, assessing its alignment with modern educational objectives and values.

Method

A multifaceted approach incorporating various research methods will be employed to achieve these aims (AbuHamda et al., 2021). Firstly, a comprehensive literature review will gather insights from scholarly works concerning homework history, effectiveness, and perceptions. Secondly, qualitative research methods such as semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions will explore teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and practices related to homework. Concurrently, observational studies will be conducted to observe teachers' behaviours and interactions about homework assignments. Finally, data collected from these different methods are analyzed using appropriate qualitative techniques to identify patterns, themes, and correlations to provide a holistic understanding of homework within educational settings.

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Thus, the present research tries to answer the following main question:

- 1- What are the underlying assumptions and beliefs guiding the implementation of homework in contemporary educational settings, and how do these influence its effectiveness and impact on student achievement?

Literature Review

Homework has been assigned to students for over a century to supplement and reinforce classroom learning, foster self-discipline and personal responsibility, and communicate with parents (Cooper, 2001; Vatterott, 2009). However, there has been much debate about the benefits and drawbacks of homework.

Several studies have found that homework can improve academic achievement, at least in older grade levels. For example, Maltese et al. (2012) analyzed data from the National Education Longitudinal Study and found that students who spent more time on homework performed better on standardized tests and earned better grades in their high school math and science courses. Similarly, Fernández-Alonso et al. (2015) found homework positively associated with math, language, and science academic performance for 15-year-old students.

However, the research is mixed on homework's benefits for elementary students. A Fan et al. (2017) meta-analysis found little to no association between homework and academic achievement for elementary school students. Similarly, Grodner and Rupp (2013) analyzed international TIMSS data and found no relationship between homework and test scores for 4th-grade students. Some studies have even found that homework may be detrimental. For example, Katz et al. (2014) found that spending over 1-2 hours per night on homework was negatively associated with standardized test scores for middle school students.

In terms of nonacademic outcomes, homework has been linked to greater self-regulation and study skills (Xu, 2005), increased parental involvement in academics (Van Voorhis, 2011), and higher ratings on work habits from teachers (Farrell & Danby, 2015). However, excessive homework has also been associated with stress, lack of leisure time, and negative attitudes toward academics (Galloway et al., 2013).

Teachers also must be prepared to for online learning give appropriate homework that meet students needs (Ismail and Dawoud, 2022). Therefore, the Palestinian textbooks should designed in a flexiable way to allow teachers create better homework for students (Ismail et al., 2022; Ismail and Naqeeb). For example, teachers can ask students to read a novel at home which may also develop students writing skill through learning grammar, new vocabs, linking words, and sentence structure (see Ismail and Mallemari, 2020).

In conclusion, the effect of homework on student achievement and other outcomes remains contested, highlighting the need for further research examining the optimal use of homework across contexts.

Results and Discussion

Nobody is sure when and where the first homework was initiated. However, it is agreed that homework is very ancient. ThroughEducation mentions that homework was invented in the ancient Roman Empire in the I century AD by an oratory teacher and philosopher, Pliny the Younger. He demanded that his students practice public speech at home to be more confident and fluent in front of people. In the 19th century, the German educational reformer Horace Man strongly promoted a compulsory national education system where pupils should complete mandatory assignments at home to achieve prosperity (ThroughEducation, 2020). By 1983, despite parents questioning homework's effect on their burnt-out children, American business and educational agenda have recommended tasking students with more homework and lengthening the school year if America is to maintain economic and scientific leadership worldwide (Gegelman,2004). In its recent form, homework is defined as " tasks assigned to students by school teachers that are meant to be carried out during non-school hours." (Cooper, 1989. P.7).

Consequently, it is implied that most of the assignments will probably be done at home, and it is supposed to support students' high achievement at school and improve their academic level towards achievement and future prosperity. Still, there is much dispute nowadays about the effectiveness of homework. Cooper et al. oppose homework in its current form mainly because of the assumed parents' intervention at home. Parents may stress the children out to meet their standards, create confusion due to different explanations of tasks from teachers, and do the homework themselves instead of their children. Besides, it enhances the discrimination between

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children because of the disparate resources and support available for children from their families. In addition, the authors have found no strong evidence of an association between doing homework and high achievement at school (Cooper et al., 2006).

It is worth mentioning that those shortcomings appear to rely on homework as a main assessment and educational tool without revisiting for checking and analyzing. Therefore, it is important to decipher different characteristics of homework as an artefact and a long-term behaviour among teachers. It is essential to understand that what makes perfect, in teachers' view, might be just a burden and overwork without the required results for students and their parents. The understanding of using homework as an artefact in our school culture is the key. Schein, Schneider, and Barsoux call for deciphering the codes of artefacts, analyzing their values and beliefs, and detecting the underlying assumptions behind them to make the utmost benefit of it (Schein, 1992) (Schneider & Barsoux, 1997). Considering the school as an educational organization in the 21st century, teachers should choose how to apply homework carefully, observe their behaviours closely, and cautiously evaluate their prior beliefs and values. In addition, teachers need to reflect on their underlying taken-of-granted assumptions about the effectiveness of homework in its constantly changing manner.

So, as already discussed, the ideal way to support homework in school culture must be based on conditions. In their research about the effectiveness of homework in mathematics, Rosario and others conclude that homework proves to be an effective artefact in enhancing the educational process. Yet, teachers need to be trained to analyze their practices carefully to determine the optimal outcome. Homework quality and quantity, frequency, students' attitudes, purpose, and degree of individualization are characteristics that may challenge even an experienced teacher. Therefore, the school administration must consider teacher training programs addressing theoretical issues pertinent to students' needs and academic progress (Rosario et al., 2019).

It's also important to remember that there is an ongoing debate on homework as a Pendulum swing between opposition and support, and it seems to have no end (Marzano & Pickering, 2007) (Galwe, 2011). Consequently, teachers must follow recent research, reconsider their beliefs, and constantly reflect on their performance to discover deep assumptions. Not only those pertinent to homework as a long-term custom but also to other artefacts, behaviours, and practices in school culture.

Conclusion

The role and effectiveness of homework have been an enduring debate in education. While homework has centuries of tradition behind it, the empirical evidence on its academic benefits remains mixed, especially for younger students. This study underscores the need to examine the assumptions and beliefs guiding homework practices critically.

Too often, homework assignments are given automatically without sufficient consideration of their purpose, design, and alignment with modern learning goals. As an artefact, homework provides a window into changing educational philosophies, from rote memorization to analytical thinking. However, many teachers' underlying rationales for assigning homework may be outdated or unexamined.

Several recommendations emerge from this research to optimize the use of homework. First, schools and teachers must scrutinize homework policies and norms against current research on their impacts across different contexts. Reflexive homework practices should be reevaluated through contemporary educational values like student engagement, critical thinking, and equity.

Second, improved teacher training is needed in designing purposeful, differentiated, and responsive homework to student needs. Teachers should be supported in analyzing their assumptions about the benefits of homework versus potential drawbacks. Their homework literacy—understanding quality, quantity, purpose, frequency, etc.—must be enhanced.

Third, homework should be implemented judiciously as one tool among many, not as the primary method of instruction or assessment. Its role should be delineated at the classroom, school, and district levels.

Finally, homework is a larger narrative about education's changing philosophies throughout history. Ensuring its effective use requires ongoing reflection, training, and alignment with modern goals and contexts. At the same time, a staple of schooling, the purpose and impacts of homework must be continually interrogated. It can be a valuable artifact supporting student learning and growth when leveraged strategically.

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